

Reusable and magnetically harvestable nanocomposite adsorbents for advanced phosphorus removal and recovery from wastewater effluents: Pilot scale application and ecotoxicity screening of their environmental safety

Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan^{*(***)}, Karl Mandel^{**}, Carsten Meyer^{***}, Mariliis Sihtmäe^{*}, Irina Blinova^{*}, Anne Kahru^{*}

^{*} National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn, Estonia: asya.drenkova@kbfi.ee | mariliis.sihtmae@kbfi.ee | irina.blinova@kbfi.ee | anne.kahru@kbfi.ee
^{**} FAU Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany: karl.mandel@fau.de
^{***} University of Stuttgart, ISWA, Stuttgart, Germany: asya.drenkova@iswa.uni-stuttgart.de | carsten.meyer@iswa.uni-stuttgart.de

INTRODUCTION

Figure 1 – Conceptual scheme of the proposed technology for phosphorus elimination and recovery with composite magnetic sorbent micro-particles. Reference: [1]

Phosphorus (P) is a key nutrient for agriculture, but also an environmental pollutant causing eutrophication, commonly removed from wastewater. Engineered nanostructured materials, predominantly metal oxides/hydroxides, are frequently reported as excellent adsorbents for phosphate, able to selectively remove P from wastewater to ultra-low concentrations, and facilitate P-recovery through reversible sorption, nevertheless, their environmental aquatic safety is rarely addressed.

The proposed technology (Fig.1) uses tailored nanocomposite adsorbent materials based on metal oxide/hydroxides deposited onto magnetic carrier particles (5–25 µm) for the selective and reversible sorption of phosphorus (P) directly from wastewater effluents. The engineered composite micro-sorbents can be extracted magnetically from water, regenerated in an alkaline solution, where P-desorption and enrichment take place, and reused again. The P-rich solution can be used as a source for further P-recovery, e.g. via precipitation of struvite. Important benefits are the ability for advanced P-removal down to ultra-low effluent concentrations <0.005 mg/L PO₄-P and <0.05 mg/L P_{total}, excluding any eutrophication risk for the receiving water body, and the option for subsequent recovery of the valuable nutrient.

Furthermore, this study assesses the ecotoxicological hazard of the proposed adsorbent materials and suggests measures to improve the eco-safety of this promising technology, so it can be a superior alternative to the conventional P removal techniques in wastewater treatment. Reference: [2]

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Pilot-scale test results for phosphate removal, enrichment and recovery from 1.5 m³ P-rich wastewater using magnetic particles modified with ZnFeZr-nanocomposite adsorbent over 20 reuse cycles

Figure 4 – Adsorption and desorption pilot results: **a)** PO₄-P concentration in the wastewater at the inflow (grey) and outflow (black) of the adsorption tank. Adsorbent dose 1 g/L, pH 7, 20 min contact time; **b)** Enrichment of phosphate ions in the NaOH desorption solution (grey bars) and conductivity (+) drop due to particles' regeneration. Reference: [4]

Figure 5 – Phosphate recovery as pure struvite crystals (slow-release fertilizer) precipitated from the P-rich reclaimed solution. Reference: [4] In the pilot test, effluent concentrations < 0.005 mg/L PO₄-P were achieved (> 99.9% P-removal). The overall P-recovery efficiency after 20 runs was 82% (95.2% adsorption; 86% desorption efficiency), leading to 38 times P-enrichment of the final reclaimed eluate (382 mg/L PO₄-P) compared to the initial phosphate concentration in the wastewater (~10 mg/L PO₄-P).

METHODS

Metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposites for selective phosphorus adsorption were synthesized via co-precipitation of 2-, 3- and 4 valent metal precursors (Zn²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe³⁺, Zr⁴⁺) at different molar ratios (see Table 1), characterized with laser diffraction, ICP-OES, SEM, XRD. Their reversible P-sorption ability was investigated intensively [3]. The best-performing composite ZnFeZr-6:1:1 was deposited onto magnetic carrier particles (5–25 µm) and tested at pilot-scale. The proof-of-concept was demonstrated successfully through a pilot test [4] where the removal, recovery and enrichment of phosphate from 1.5 m³ secondary municipal effluent was achieved throughout 20 cycles of particles' regeneration and reuse, as shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2 – Pilot plant set-up for removal and recovery of phosphate from municipal wastewater effluent with magnetic nanocomposite sorbent particles. Reference: [4]

To verify the environmental compatibility and safe-by-design nature of the proposed sorbent materials for WWTP effluent treatment, an ecotoxicological hazard assessment was performed with the 11 most efficient metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposite P-adsorbents using ISO- and OECD-standardized high-to-medium throughput ecotoxicity tests involving 3 different food-web level aquatic organisms: naturally bioluminescent marine bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, crustacean *Daphnia magna* and freshwater green algae *R. subcapitata*, as summarized in Fig.3. The pilot-scale tested ZnFeZr-6:1:1 oxyhydroxide was modified further by reducing the zinc fraction to minimize the leaching of toxic Zn²⁺ ions.

Figure 3 – Ecotoxicological tests based on standard ISO and OECD protocols with 3 different model aquatic organisms (bacteria *V. fischeri*, crustacean *D. magna* and algae *R. subcapitata*) used to assess the toxic potency (half-effective concentration EC₅₀ & minimum bactericidal concentration MBC) of 11 nanocomposite P-adsorbents.

Advanced P-elimination and WWTP effluent polishing with the magnetic ZnFeZr-nanocomposite adsorbent

Figure 6 – Advanced phosphorus elimination and polishing of a municipal WWTP effluent over 55 cycles of particles regeneration and reuse, reaching ultra-low total P concentration (blue bars) after treatment with the magnetic adsorbents. Reference: [1]

Remarks:
 Beige bars: inflow total phosphorus P_{tot,in} (PO₄-P+ΔP) concentrations in the wastewater to be treated (secondary clarifier effluent).
 Adsorption: pH 7, 20 min contact time.
 Blue bars: outflow total phosphorus P_{tot,out} conc. after treatment with the particles.
 "ΔP=P_{tot}-PO₄-P" is the unreactive phosphorus fraction (dissolved and particulate).

Toxicity results of 11 metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposite P-adsorbents to 3 model aquatic organisms

Table 1 – Toxic potency results: EC₅₀ (half-effective concentration) and MBC (minimum bactericidal concentration) of 11 nanocomposite P-adsorbents, their 0.1µm-filtered supernatants and soluble precursor metal salts. All values are average (n=3) with 95% confidence intervals in parenthesis. Ref.: [2].

Composites	Composite Name	Bacteria <i>Vibrio fischeri</i>		Crustacean <i>D. magna</i>		Algae <i>R. subcapitata</i>	
		30-min EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	Zn-normalized 30-min EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	24-h EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	48-h EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	72-h EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	72-h EC ₅₀ (mg/L)
Composites	ZnFeZr-18:5:1	36.9 (29.0-49.0)	13.5 (10.6-17.9)	100	4.38 (4.06-4.83)	0.045 (0.001-0.090)	
	ZnFeZr-10:1:1	53.9 (41.0-70.0)	20.0 (15.2-25.9)	250	6.48 (5.31-7.78)	0.102 (0.049-0.113)	
	ZnFeZr-6:1:1	118.0 (93.8-127.0)	30.9 (24.3-33.2)	250	7.69 (5.99-8.88)	0.195 (0.184-0.202)	
	ZnFeZr-4:1:1	118.3 (104.8-131.0)	28.7 (25.3-31.6)	100	9.01 (7.34-11.23)	0.150 (0.132-0.164)	
	ZnFeZr-3:6:0:2:1	118.2 (114.0-127.0)	42.7 (35.8-44.9)	250	5.74 (4.66-7.29)	0.180 (0.097-0.111)	
	CaFe-2:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>100	0.317 (0.287-0.353)	
	CaFeZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>100	0.301 (0.279-0.325)	
	CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	112.5 (90.9-117.8)	20.6 (16.6-21.5)	250	12.54 (9.94-14.98)	0.208 (0.157-0.260)	
	MgZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>100	0.474 (0.424-0.539)	
	MgZr-1:1:1	484 (391-596)	81.4 (65.5-100)	>1000	>100	0.222 (0.197-0.252)	
	ZnFeZr-1:1:1@MPs	112.5 (92.9-127)	58.8 (66.6-61.0)	>1000	>100	3.81 (3.31-4.39)	
Supernatants (0.1µm-filtered)	(S)-ZnFeZr-18:5:1	1645 (1407-1713)	601 (514-629)	>2500	>100		
(S)-ZnFeZr-10:1:1	2011 (1713-2149)	944 (634-795)	>2500				
(S)-ZnFeZr-6:1:1	799 (666-778)	209 (174-204)	>2500				
(S)-ZnFeZr-4:1:1	1002 (853-983)	242 (206-237)	>2500				
(S)-ZnFeZr-3:6:0:2:1	1395 (1218-1391)	324 (309-353)	>2500				
(S)-CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	490 (454-465)	90 (78-90)	>2500				
(S)-ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs	13637 (8496-13853)	457 (253-1067)	>5000				
Precursor metal salts (stocks 2 g-Me/L)	ZnCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O pH 6.4	17.47 (14.44-17.99)	n.a.	50	n.a.	0.114 (0.103-0.123)	
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O pH 1.9*	1.22 (1.12-1.25)*	n.a.	5*	n.a.	n.a.		
ZnO·xH ₂ O pH 1.8*	2.20 (2.12-2.22)*	n.a.	10*	n.a.	n.a.		
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O pH 6.8	non-toxic	n.a.	>1000	n.a.	n.a.		
MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O pH 6.8	non-toxic	n.a.	>1000	n.a.	n.a.		
Positive controls (stock 5 µg-Zn/L)	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (as Zn ²⁺)	7.80 (7.10-8.50)	n.a.	50	n.a.	CaSO ₄ 0.02 (0.016-0.031)	
Very toxic	EC ₅₀ ≤ 10 mg/L						
Toxic	10 < EC ₅₀ ≤ 100 mg/L						
Harmful	100 < EC ₅₀ ≤ 1000 mg/L						
Not classified / not harmful	EC ₅₀ > 1000 mg/L						

Figure 7 – Microscopic images visualizing the immobilization of *D. magna* due to agglomeration effects and ingestion of nanocomposites (left); Fluorescence microscopy of algal growth inhibition due to entrapment in particle agglomerates (right).

Figure 8 – Colony forming ability ("Spot Test") of bacteria *V. fischeri* after 24h exposure to: a) synthesized nanocomposites; b) pilot-scale tested ZnFeZr-6:1:1, its magnetic version ZnFeZr@MPs and their particle-free supernatants. Reference: [2]

CONCLUSIONS

- Promising sorption-based technology for advanced P-removal and P-recovery from pre-treated wastewater.
- Proof-of-concept verified via successful upscaling of adsorbent synthesis and efficient magnetic harvesting.
- Regeneration and reuse of the nanocomposite adsorbents demonstrated throughout numerous cycles.
- Ultra-low effluent concentrations achievable: < 50 µg/L total P (dissolved + particulate) and < 5 µg/L PO₄-P.
- Total efficiency of P-recovery > 90% under optimal conditions. Struvite crystals with high purity from P-rich eluate.
- However, not all composites are "safe-by-design". May pose ecotoxic hazard if released in the aquatic environment.
- All Zn-containing composites had inhibitory effects to bacteria *V. fischeri*, were toxic to *D. magna* and very toxic to algae.
- Algae are the most sensitive organism. Toxicity mechanisms: 1) Direct toxicity via dissolution of bioavailable Zn²⁺ ions, ingestion of nanoparticles, etc.; 2) Indirect toxicity through nutrients removal from the algal medium; 3) Agglomeration effects - immobilization of daphnids, growth inhibition due to entrapment of algae within particle agglomerates.
- Not recommended to apply the adsorbents directly in the biological treatment step of WWTP - biomass growth inhibition!
- Good chemical/mechanical stability is a must! Adsorbents harvesting must be well-secured within the engineering facility.

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* National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn, Estonia, asya.drenkova@kbfi.ee

** FAU Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany, karl.mandel@fau

*** University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany, carsten.meyer@iswa.uni-stuttgart.de

**** National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn, Estonia, mariliis.sihtmae@kbfi.ee

***** National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn, Estonia, irina.blinova@kbfi.ee

***** National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn, Estonia, anne.kahru@kbfi.ee

Abstract: The proposed technology uses tailored nanocomposite adsorbent materials based on metal oxide/hydroxides deposited onto magnetic carrier particles (5-25 μm) for the selective and reversible sorption of phosphorus (P) directly from wastewater effluents. The engineered composite micro-sorbents can be extracted magnetically from water, regenerated in an alkaline solution, where P desorption and enrichment take place, and reused again. The P-rich solution can be used as a source for further P-recovery, e.g. via precipitation of struvite. Important benefits are the ability for advanced P-removal down to ultra-low effluent concentrations $< 0.005 \text{ mg/L PO}_4\text{-P}$ and $< 0.05 \text{ mg/L P}_{\text{total}}$, excluding any eutrophication risk for the receiving waters, and the option for subsequent recovery of the valuable nutrient. Furthermore, this study assesses the ecotoxicological hazard of the proposed adsorbent materials and suggests measures to improve the eco-safety of this promising technology, so it can be a superior alternative to the conventional P-removal techniques in wastewater treatment.

Keywords: Aquatic toxicity; Zn-containing nanocomposite adsorbents; Phosphorus removal and recovery; Safe-by-design; Wastewater effluent polishing

Phosphorus (P) is a key nutrient for agriculture, but also an environmental pollutant causing eutrophication, commonly removed from wastewater. Engineered nanostructured materials, predominantly metal oxides/hydroxides, are frequently reported as excellent adsorbents for phosphate, able to selectively remove P from wastewater to ultra-low concentrations and facilitate P-recovery through reversible sorption (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016), but their environmental aquatic safety is rarely addressed.

This study reports the high P-removal and P-recovery efficiency ($>90\%$) from a pilot-scale test with the engineered adsorbents and assesses the ecotoxicological hazard of the 10 most efficient metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposite P-adsorbents using toxicity tests involving two different food-web level aquatic organisms: the naturally bioluminescent marine bacterium *Vibrio fischeri* and the crustacean *Daphnia magna*. Nanocomposites were synthesized via co-precipitation of 2-, 3- and 4-valent metal precursors (Zn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zr^{4+}) at different molar ratios, and characterized with laser diffraction, ICP-OES, XRD and SEM. Among these, the pilot-scale tested ZnFeZr-6:1:1-oxyhydroxide was modified by reducing the zinc-fraction to minimize leaching of toxic Zn^{2+} ions. Composites stability was investigated by addressing agglomeration, settling and solubilization (release of metal ions and/or potentially hazardous nanoparticles) in wastewater and various test media.

The scheme in Fig. 1.1 shows a conceptual overview of the proposed technology for reversible sorption of phosphorus using nanocomposite magnetic carrier particles, modified with a tailored P-selective adsorbent.

Figure 1.1 Conceptual scheme of the proposed technology for phosphorus elimination and recovery with composite magnetic sorbent micro-particles.

Earlier research (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017) demonstrated the successful proof-of-concept through a pilot test where the removal, recovery and enrichment of phosphate from 1.5 m³ secondary municipal effluent was achieved throughout 20 cycles of particles' regeneration and reuse, as shown in Fig. 1.2.

Figure 1.2 Pilot plant set up for removal and recovery of phosphate from municipal wastewater effluent with composite magnetic particles (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the technology has proven its potential to remove other P-species, besides ortho-phosphate, and achieve ultra-low effluent concentrations (< 0.005 mg/L $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ and < 0.05 mg/L P_{tot}). The results in Fig. 1.3 demonstrate the ability of the magnetic adsorbents to polish a municipal wastewater effluent consistently over 55 cycles by reducing the unreactive phosphorus fraction, which can not be removed economically with conventional techniques (chemical precipitation or EBPR). The beige bars represent the total phosphorus concentrations $\text{P}_{\text{tot,in}}$ ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P} + \Delta\text{P}$) in the wastewater (secondary effluent) to be treated. The blue bars show the outflow total phosphorus concentrations $\text{P}_{\text{tot,out}}$ after the treatment with the particles. Remark: “ $\Delta\text{P} = \text{P}_{\text{tot}} - \text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ ” is the unreactive phosphorus fraction (dissolved and particulate).

Figure 1.3 Advanced phosphorus elimination and polishing of a municipal WWTP effluent, reaching ultra-low total phosphorus (P_{tot}) concentration after treatment with the magnetic adsorbent particles (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2021).

As a next important step, all as-synthesized nanocomposites, their filtered supernatants and precursor metal salts were evaluated for their toxic potency (half-effective concentration, EC_{50} and minimum bactericidal concentration, MBC) using 3 different ISO and OECD standardized tests: *Vibrio fischeri* 30-min bioluminescence inhibition assay (ISO-21338:2010), *V. fischeri* 24-h viability assay (‘Spot test’) and *Daphnia magna* 48-h acute immobilization test (OECD-202).

The ecotoxicity screening results in Table 1.1 show that only the Zn-containing composites showed inhibitory effects to both test organisms. Those with the highest zinc-fraction (ZnFeZr-18:5:1; ZnFeZr-10:1:1) were classified “harmful” to *V. fischeri* ($10 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 100$ mg/L) and toxic to *D. magna* ($1 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 10$ mg/L), therefore, environmentally unsafe for engineering applications. The ZnFeZr-6:1:1 (*V. fischeri* $\text{EC}_{50} = 118$ mg/L; *D. magna* $\text{EC}_{50} = 7.7$ mg/L) proved to be safe for both aquatic organisms once deposited on magnetic particles ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs ($\text{EC}_{50} \gg 100$ mg/L, $\text{MBC} > 1000$ mg/L). All other composites without Zn were non-toxic, neither to *Vibrio fischeri*, nor to the more sensitive *Daphnia magna*.

Table 1.1 Toxicity results to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and crustacean *Daphnia magna* of all as-synthesized metal oxide/hydroxide composites. The listed 30 min EC₅₀ values are average (n=3) with the respective 95% confidence intervals included in parenthesis. The 24-h MBC values are representative for three repetitive tests (n=3) with two parallels each. All concentrations (mg-compound/L) are nominal (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2024).

Remark: **EC₅₀**: half-effective concentration; **MBC**: minimum bactericidal concentration.

Nanocomposite Name	<i>Vibrio fischeri</i>			<i>Daphnia magna</i>
	30-min EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	Zn-normalized 30-min EC ₅₀ (mg/L)	24-h MBC (mg/L)	48-h EC ₅₀ (mg/L)
ZnFeZr-18:5:1	36.9 (29.0-49.0)	13.5 (10.6-17.9)	100	4.38 (4.06-4.83)
ZnFeZr-10:1:1	53.9 (41.0-70.0)	20.0 (15.2-25.9)	250	6.48 (5.31-7.78)
ZnFeZr-6:1:1	118.0 (93.8-127.0)	30.9 (24.5-33.2)	250	7.69 (5.59-9.88)
ZnFeZr-4:1:1	118.8 (104.8-131.0)	28.7 (25.3-31.6)	100	9.01 (7.34-11.23)
ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1	168.2 (141.0-177.0)	42.7 (35.8-44.9)	250	5.74 (4.66-7.20)
CaFe-2:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>> 100
CaFeZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>> 100
CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	112.5 (90.9-117.8)	20.6 (16.6-21.5)	250	12.54 (9.94-14.98)
MgFeZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	>> 100
MgZnFe-1:1:1	486 (391-598)	81.4 (65.5-100)	>1000	> 100
ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs	1123 (929-1173)	58.8 (48.6-61.4)	>1000	>> 100

Very toxic EC ₅₀ ≤ 1 mg/L	Toxic 1 < EC ₅₀ ≤ 10 mg/L	Harmful 10 < EC ₅₀ ≤ 100 mg/L	Not classified / not harmful EC ₅₀ > 100 mg/L
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